

Horizon Europe

User Manual - EagleEye Printer

Document description

Name	User Manual – EagleEye Printer
Format	Portable Document Format (.pdf)
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1. Introduction

The EagleEye printer represents an advanced 3D printing approach that optimizes two-photon polymerization (2PP) for large-area processing. It integrates 2PP with digital light processing (DLP)—a lower-resolution but highly efficient printing technique—into a single optical setup. This integration enables a layer-by-layer printing process in which DLP is used for bulk structures or areas with less detail, while 2PP is reserved for features requiring fine resolution.

Rather than accelerating 2PP, the EagleEye approach applies it selectively where high precision is essential, preserving its resolution capabilities. Notably, each technique can also be used independently, maximizing the printer's versatility. Moreover, 2PP can achieve varying levels of precision and resolution by using different objective lenses within a single 3D printing job. This flexibility is facilitated by a motorized turret that allows seamless switching between three different objective lenses. A schematic illustration of the EagleEye printer is shown in Figure 1.

The following document, titled *User Manual – EagleEye Printer*, provides detailed specifications of the printer and outlines the software operation, particularly for the DLP system. Notably, this user manual is exclusively designed for the printer developed under the EagleEye project (MSCA-PF 2021: 101059253, <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101059253>).

For 2PP, custom-designed software was utilized to perform the process and slicer 3D computer designs. However, the EagleEye printer was intentionally designed to ensure compatibility with various 2PP configurations, making the system highly adaptable to future advancements in 3D printing. This includes not only 2PP and DLP but also other stereolithography (SLA) techniques.

Figure 1 Rendered image and schematic illustration of the EagleEye printer.

2. Specification of the EagleEye printer

The 2PP setup in the EagleEye printer comprises an ultrafast laser system (FemtoFiber Ultra 780, Toptica Photonics AG) with a central wavelength of 780 nm, a pulse duration of 150 fs, and a repetition rate of 80 MHz. Additional components included a 2D galvo scanner, an acoustic-optical modulator (MTS40-A3-750.850, AA Opto Electronics) serving as a shutter, and three linear translation stages (M-605.1DD, Physik Instrumente), enabling precise beam guidance and sample movement for layer-by-layer 3D printing via 2PP.

For dynamic objective switching, a motorized objective lens turret was custom-built. The turret provides a maximum travel range of 110 mm and is designed to accommodate three standard dry objective lenses with different numerical apertures (NAs). Its maximum payload capacity is 2 kg.

A micro stepper motor facilitates precise movement between the objectives, achieving a resolution of approximately 0.16 μm . The turret can be controlled using a microcontroller, specifically an Arduino Uno. Further specifications are depicted in Figure 2.

Specifications	
Communication Interface	RS-232
Power Supply	12V, 2A
Axes of Motion	1
Operating Temperature Range	0 to 50 °C
Stage Material	Anodized aluminum
Travel Range	110 mm
Resolution	Adjustable, depending on microstepping
Repeatability	< 9 microns
Accuracy	< 30 microns
Maximum Speed	10 mm/s
Payload Capacity	2 kg (tested)
Drive Mechanism	Ballscrew
Ballscrew Pitch	1mm
Stepper Motor Model	NEMA 17
Mounting Interface	Angle Bracket with hole pattern
Microstepping Options	1/2, 1/4, 1/8, 1/16, 1/32
Limit Switches	2 Hard Limit Switches
Home Position	Center Position and Negative Limit

Resolution by Microstepping Level	Resolution (μm per step)
Full Step (1)	5.0
1/2 Step	2.5
1/4 Step	1.25
1/8 Step	0.625
1/16 Step	0.3125
1/32 Step	0.15625

Figure 2 Specification of objective lens turret.

The DLP setup utilized a commercially available device, the DLP LightCrafter E4500MKII+2W (EKB Technologies Ltd, [link](#)). This device is equipped with a DLP 0.45 WXGA chipset (Texas Instruments), offering a binary pattern rate of 4225 Hz and an 8-bit grayscale pattern rate of 120 Hz, with a resolution of 800 \times 1280 pixels.

It features a high-power UV-LED emitting light at 405 nm with a 2W output, making it suitable for rapidly curing most standard resins at working distances ranging from 25 mm to 34 cm. In the EagleEye printer, the DLP system was configured at a working distance where the UV light projected onto an area of 64 mm \times 40 mm, resulting in a pixel resolution of approximately 50 μm .

3. Software

3.1. 2PP software

2PP, including objective lens switching, was performed using the software *Arachne*, a beta version of the commercially available software *Cicada* distributed by Biomimetics, Greece (<https://www.biomimetic.gr/service/laser-processing-software/>). *Cicada* provides a hardware-independent software solution for both additive and subtractive manufacturing.

For further details, please visit <https://www.biomimetic.gr>.

3.2. DLP control software

While *Cicada* has the potential to enable simultaneous operation of DLP and 2PP, the EagleEye printer includes a self-developed DLP control software that can be operated through a graphical user interface (GUI). The software and its source code are available on the Zenodo repository via the following link: <https://zenodo.org/records/14616141>. The source code is optimized for execution using Python 3.8.10. The DLP control software is compatible with both Windows and macOS systems.

An illustration of the GUI is provided in Figure 3. Upon activation of the software, a black image is automatically loaded onto the DLP, ensuring that no polymerization occurs before the printing process is initialized.

Figure 3 Graphic user interface of DLP control software.

The graphical user interface (GUI) consists of four main sections:

1. **Connection Controls**
2. **Movement Controls**
3. **Image Control**
4. **Printing Settings**

Connection Control

The **Connection Control** section allows the user to manage the connection to the stage. To establish a connection, the user can click the **Connect Stage** button. Once connected, the stage will be initialized and ready for operation.

To disconnect the stage, the user can simply click the **Disconnect Stage** button.

Before starting the process, the user should move the stage to the desired starting position and click **Set Home** to define the home position for the process.

An illustration of the **Connection Control** section is provided in Figure 5.

Figure 4 Connection Controls.

Movement Controls

The **Movement Controls** section enables users to manually control the movement of the stage. To move the stage in the X, Y, or Z direction, the respective buttons (**Move X**, **Move Y**, or **Move Z**) can be clicked. The stage will travel the distance specified under **Move Step [μm]** at the velocity set under **Stage Velocity [mm/s]**.

Both the **Move Step** and **Stage Velocity** parameters can be adjusted individually. To ensure safe operation and prevent the stage from colliding with the resin tank, the maximum allowable value for **Move Step** is limited to 1000 μm. Similarly, the maximum **Stage Velocity** is capped at 7 mm/s.

It is important to note that the velocity set under **Stage Velocity** will also be applied during the printing process.

An illustration of the **Movement Controls** section is provided in Figure 5.

Figure 5 Movement Controls.

Image Control

The **Image Control** section allows users to manually set the image size for printing. Ideally, these settings should match the size of the image generated, such as by slicing an STL file, as described later in Section XX. Specifically, for the DLP integrated into the EagleEye printer, the maximum pixel dimensions are:

- **Image Width (Px number W):** 1280 pixels
- **Image Length (Px number L):** 800 pixels

These settings are applied throughout the printing process to ensure the image is printed at the specified scale.

Additionally, the software provides a feature for testing image projection. Users can load static images by clicking the **Load Static** button. This action opens a folder browser, allowing the user to select the desired image, which will then be displayed continuously until further action is taken. To revert to the default black image, users can click the **Load Black** button.

An illustration of the **Image Control** section is provided in Figure 6.

Figure 6 Image Control.

Printing Settings

The **Printing Settings** section allows users to define key parameters for the printing process:

- **Exposure 1st Layer [s]:** This parameter sets the exposure time for the bottom layer to ensure proper adhesion of the polymerized material to the substrate.
- **Number of bottom layers:** Users can specify the number of bottom layers to be printed.
- **Exposure time [s]:** This defines the exposure time for each image of each layer, determining how long the image is projected to polymerize the layer in the shape of the specific image.
- **Layer Distance [μm]:** This sets the distance between consecutive layers during printing. For 3D models, this value should match the layer thickness defined in the slicing software.
- **Lower Stage between each layer [μm]:** This specifies how far the stage is lowered after completing the printing of a single layer. The stage travels into the material to ensure that fresh photosensitive material coats the surface of the polymerized volume, preparing it for the next layer.

Once these parameters, along with others such as image size (see **Image Control**), are set, the automated printing process can be initialized by clicking the **Load Images and Start Printing** button. This action opens a folder browser, allowing the user to select the folder containing the desired images. The images will be loaded in order based on their file names, and the printing process will conclude once the final image has been projected. Notably, the printing process will not start if the user has not defined an initial position, which can be set by clicking the **Set Home** button (see **Movement Controls**).

To close the software, the user can simply click the **Exit** button

An illustration of the **Printing Settings** section is provided in Figure 7. The listed parameters are typical values used in the EagleEye project (MSCA-PF 2021: 101059253, <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101059253>).

Parameter	Value
Exposure 1st Layer [s]	20
Numbers of bottom layer	3
Exposure time [s]	2
Layer Distance [um]	100
Lower Stage between each layer [um]	5000

Buttons: Load images and start printing, Exit

Figure 7 Printing setting Control.

Delays

Delays before and after projecting an image, specifically implemented to compensate for stage oscillation when reaching the desired position, were optimized as part of EagleEye project (MSCA-PF 2021: 101059253, <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101059253>). Users can adjust these delays directly to their needs by modifying the source code.

4. Slicing software for DLP

The slicing of 3D computer designs must be operated directly via the source code. The source code can be accessed through the Zenodo repository using the link <https://zenodo.org/records/14616141>, and it is also listed in Section 5.

The source code is optimized for execution using Python 3.8.10 and is compatible with both Windows and macOS systems. It is recommended to use Visual Studio Code for running the slicer.

At the end of the source code, users will find the following section. Notably, the slicer works with 3D computer design in STL format.

```
if __name__ == '__main__':
    image_slicer=ImageSlicer("/Users/XXX/Desktop/DLP/DLPControl/Bowtie.stl")
    ### Set the image size
    image_slicer.image_width=300
    image_slicer.image_height=300
    #Set color for background of image and polygon infill
    image_slicer.background_color="black"
    image_slicer.polygon_color="white"
    #Create layers on Z axis with specific step and create the polygons
    z_slices=image_slicer.create_layers(z_step=3)
    polygons=image_slicer.get_polygons_from_slices(z_slices)
    # Iterate through the polygons and create images from them
    for i,polygon in enumerate(polygons):
        image,drawing=image_slicer.polygons_to_image(polygon,scale=1)
        # Show Image
        #image.show()
        #Save Image
        image.save(f"slice_{i}.png")
```

In this section, users must specify the path to the STL file they wish to slice. Using the **polygon_scale** parameter, users can further scale their 3D computer designs, although it is recommended to design the model with the intended printing dimensions to avoid scaling issues.

Additionally, users can define the image size, which should correspond to the desired image size for printing via the **DLP control software** (see *Image Control*).

Once all parameters have been set, the user can execute the slicer. Upon completion, the sliced files will be generated as PNG images and saved in the same folder as the source code file. The images are named sequentially as "**slice_NUMBER**", ensuring proper order for printing the structures using the **DLP control software**.

An illustration of the a sliced STL is provided in Figure 8.

Figure 8 Sliced STL file.

5. Source code of slicing software

```

import trimesh
from shapely.geometry import Polygon, MultiPolygon
from PIL import Image, ImageDraw
import numpy as np

class ImageSlicer():
    def __init__(self, stl_path: str):
        '''Load STL File'''
        self.mesh = trimesh.load(stl_path)
        self.mesh.rezero()
        self.slice_normal = [0, 0, 1]
        self._width = 1000
        self._height = 1000
        self._background_color = "black"
        self._polygon_color = "white"

    def create_layers(self, z_step: float, offset_bottom: float = 0, offset_top: float = 0) -
    > np.array:
        '''Creates the Z slices depending on the step and the bounds of the mesh'''
        z_min, z_max = self.mesh.bounds[0][2] + offset_bottom,
self.mesh.bounds[1][2] + offset_top # Z-axis bounds of the mesh
        z_slices = np.arange(z_min, z_max, z_step) # Z coordinates for slices
        return z_slices

    def get_polygons_from_slices(self, z_slices):
        '''Creates polygons from the z slices'''
        polygons_full = []
        for i, z in enumerate(z_slices):
            slice_origin = [0, 0, z]
            slice_section = self.mesh.section(plane_origin=slice_origin,
plane_normal=self.slice_normal)

            # Check if slice was successfully created and is a Path2D
            if slice_section is not None:
                # Convert Path2D entities to Shapely polygons
                slice_2d, _ = slice_section.to_planar()
                polygons = slice_2d.polygons_full
                polygons_full.append(polygons)
        return polygons_full

    @property
    def image_width(self):
        return self._width

    @image_width.setter
    def image_width(self, width_value):
        '''Sets the width of the image'''
        self._width = width_value

```



```

@property
def image_height(self):
    return self._height

@image_height.setter
def image_height(self,height_value):
    '''Sets the height of the image'''
    self._height=height_value

@property
def background_color(self):
    return self._background_color

@background_color.setter
def background_color(self,background_color_value):
    '''Sets the background color of the image'''
    self._background_color=background_color_value

@property
def polygon_color(self):
    return self._polygon_color

@polygon_color.setter
def polygon_color(self,polygon_color_value):
    '''Sets the color of the polygon'''
    self._polygon_color=polygon_color_value

def create_template_image(self):
    '''Creates the template image to store the polygon'''
    img = Image.new("1", (self.image_width,self.image_height),
self.background_color)
    draw = ImageDraw.Draw(img)
    return img,draw

def polygons_to_image(self,polygons:list,scale:float=1)->tuple:
    '''Creates an image from the polygons with the color specified from the
property'''
    img,draw=self.create_template_image()
    # Draw only the outer polygons in black and leave holes in white
    for polygon in polygons:
        if isinstance(polygon, Polygon):
            # Draw the exterior of the polygon in black
            exterior_coords = [(x*scale+self.image_width/2 ,
y*scale+self.image_height/2)for x, y in polygon.exterior.coords]
            draw.polygon(exterior_coords, fill=self.polygon_color)

            # Draw each interior (hole) in white
            for hole in polygon.interiors:
                hole_coords = [(x*scale+self.image_width/2,
y*scale+self.image_height/2) for x, y in hole.coords]
                draw.polygon(hole_coords, fill=self.background_color)

```



```
        elif isinstance(polygon, MultiPolygon):
            for poly in polygon.geoms:
                exterior_coords = [(x*scale+self.image_width/2,
y*scale+self.image_height/2) for x, y in poly.exterior.coords]
                draw.polygon(exterior_coords, fill=self.polygon_color)
                for hole in poly.interiors:
                    hole_coords = [(x*scale+self.image_width/2,
y*scale+self.image_height/2) for x, y in hole.coords]
                    draw.polygon(hole_coords, fill=self.background_color)
            return img,draw

if __name__ == '__main__':
    image_slicer=ImageSlicer("/Users/XXX/Desktop/DLP/DLPControl/Bowtie.stl")
    ### Set the image size
    image_slicer.image_width=300
    image_slicer.image_height=300
    #Set color for background of image and polygon infill
    image_slicer.background_color="black"
    image_slicer.polygon_color="white"
    #Create layers on Z axis with specific step and create the polygons
    z_slices=image_slicer.create_layers(z_step=3)
    polygons=image_slicer.get_polygons_from_slices(z_slices)
    # Iterate through the polygons and create images from them
    for i,polygon in enumerate(polygons):
        image,drawing=image_slicer.polygons_to_image(polygon,scale=1)
        # Show Image
        #image.show()
        #Save Image
        image.save(f"slice_{i}.png")
```